

SensApp

D1.6 Technical/scientific review meeting 1 documents

Grant Agreement Number	829104
Project Name	Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach
Project Acronym	SensApp
Start date of the project	01/01/2019
End date of the project	31/12/2021
Work package producing the document	WP1 – Management and dissemination
Deliverable identifier	D1.6
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead beneficiary	CNR
Contributors	All participants
Dissemination level	PU (Public)
Author(s)	Veronica Vespini
Version	V1.0
Due date	31 Jan 2020
Delivery date	16/02/2020

Table of contents

- Consortium
- Executive Summary

Consortium

	Name	Short Name	Country
1	National Research Council of Italy - Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems	CNR	Italy
2	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	VUB	Belgium
3	IRCCS Centre “Bonino Pulejo”	PULEJO	Italy
4	Universitat Linz	JKU	Finland
5	Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	VTT	Austria
6	Ginolis Oy	GIN	Finland

Executive Summary

This deliverable contains following documents:

- Finalized agenda
- All power point presentations to be held during the 1st review meeting

SensApp

1ST REVIEW MEETING – AGENDA –

Project: Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach

Acronym: SensApp

GA Number: 829104

Topic: FET OPEN-01-2018-2019-2020 - FET-Open Challenging Current Thinking

Date: 19th February 2020

Location: Research Executive Agency (REA), Brussels

Aim of the meeting: Assessment of work accomplished in the period 19/01/01 – 19/12/31 (i.e. months M1 – M12)

8:30 – 9:00 Arrival and registration

9:00 – 9:30 PO's meeting with the Experts/Project monitors

Time	Topic	Speaker
9:30 – 9:40	Welcome and introduction	Ioannis Fiamegkos (REA)
9:40 – 10:00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project consortium partners' introduction - Project overview and progress - Achievements overview 	Simonetta Grilli (CNR)
10:00 – 10:30	<p>WP1 (Management and dissemination)</p> <p>Overview of the WP</p> <p>Progress of the activities</p> <p>Deliverables</p> <p>D1.1 Logo and webpage</p> <p>D1.2 IP Agreement</p> <p>D1.3 Plan for data management</p> <p>D1.4 First plan for dissemination and exploitation</p> <p>D1.5 Flyers with project targets and first results and promotional movie</p>	Simonetta Grilli (CNR)

10:30 – 10:50 Coffee break

10:50 – 11:20	WP2 (Fixing the basic elements & protocols) Overview of the WP Progress of the activities Deliverables D2.1 User requirements specification D2.2 Functional and design specifications Milestone MS1 (Strategies for integration procedure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simonetta Grilli (CNR) • Simona Itri (CNR) • Danila del Giudice (CNR)
11:20 – 12:00	WP3 (Design and micro-engineering for the super-sensor building blocks) Overview of the WP Progress of the activities	Heidi Ottevaere (VUB)
12:00 – 12:15	WP4 (Full integration & packaging of the super-sensor) WP5 (Preliminary tests in a clinical setting) Overview on future work for the next period	Sanna Uusitalo (VTT) Emanuela Mazzon (PULEJO)
12:15– 12:30	Conclusions & near future work	Simonetta Grilli (CNR)

12:30 – 14:00 Lunch break

14:00 – 15:00	Session for Commission and project monitors
15:00 – 16:00	Session for feedback from Commission and project monitors

16:00 Close

PARTICIPANTS

European Commission (Chair) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ioannis Fiamegkos
Review Team <i>Monitor Experts</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patrizia Mecocci, Institute of Gerontology and Geriatrics – Department of Medicine, University of Perugia, Clinical Unit of Geriatrics, Ospedale S. Maria della Misericordia Perugia, Italy • Constantine Stalikas, Department of Chemistry, University of Ioannina, Greece • Andrea Cusano, Engineering Department of University of Sannio, Italy
<i>Innovation Radar Expert</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Juan Pita Almenar, Department of Neurosciences – Neurodegenerative diseases Research and Development, Janssen Pharmaceutica NV.
Consortium (names of attendees to be confirmed) CNR; VUB; PULEJO; JKU; VTT; GIN

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

Project Overview

Simonetta Grilli, CNR

Objective

Development of a demonstrator of *super-sensor* able to detect Alzheimer's disease (AD) biomarkers (β -Amyloid; tau; P-tau) in human plasma

betaAmyloid protein

Technology

An innovative “droplet split-and-stack” technology for accumulating biomarker molecules onto a reaction support for successive immunoreaction

Side view of p-jetting

Motivation

Current AD diagnosis requires the determination of biomarkers in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)

lumbar puncture
&
CSF collection

Perspectives

- Rapid and non-invasive AD diagnosis by blood test
- Screening programs
- Possibility for follow-up therapies

Reference procedure: ELISA-like assays

ELISA in case of low abundant molecules

- Reaction volumes around 100 μL
- Sensitivity range 50-100 pg/mL
- Low abundant molecules \rightarrow undetectable!

- Sub- μL reaction volume
- High fluorescence signal per unit area
- Expected sensitivity: much below 1 pg/mL

THE SPLIT-AND-STACK CONCEPT

THE LEGEND	
	loading support with μ -orifice
	reaction support
	pyroelectric slab
	integrated thermal source
	fluorescence product
	primary antibody

Bench-top and fully automated instrument

FIG.4: The envisaged super-sensor

Material used nowadays in CNR labs (ISASI, Pozzuoli)

- c-cut crystals of LiNbO_3 or LiTaO_3
- 500 μm thick
- Optically polished on both sides
- High spontaneous polarization P_s ($\sim 78 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$)

Side view of a ferroelectric crystal (room temperature)

Transient uncompensated charges generate high electric field

$$\Delta P_s \propto \Delta T$$

Case of NO electric field

Case of electric field generated pyroelectrically

Side view of the typical jets

nature nanotechnology

ARTICLES

PUBLISHED ONLINE: 9 MAY 2010 | DOI: 10.1038/NNANO.2010.82

Dispensing nano-pico droplets and liquid patterning by pyroelectrodynamics shooting

P. Ferraro*, S. Coppola, S. Grilli*, M. Paturzo and V. Vespini

FL = fluorescence

FIG.2: The bulk p-jet

Typical scanner image of FL spots

500 ng/mL 300 pg/mL 60 pg/mL 30 pg/mL 15 pg/mL 3 pg/mL

- Collagen solution
- Spot diameter around 600 μ m
- Challenging SNR at 3 pg/mL

ARTICLE

Received 13 Mar 2014 | Accepted 18 Sep 2014 | Published 19 Nov 2014

DOI: 10.1038/ncomms6314

Active accumulation of very diluted biomolecules by nano-dispensing for easy detection below the femtomolar range

S. Grilli¹, L. Miccio¹, O. Gennari¹, S. Coppola¹, V. Vespi¹, L. Battista¹, P. Orlando^{1,2} & P. Ferraro^{1,3}

SensApp Project	
Duration	Start: 1 st January 2019 End: 31 st December 2021
Overall budget	3.287.562,50 € (75% pre-paid)
Partners	6
Work Packages	5
Deliverables	24 (12 public; 12 confidential)
Milestones	4
Project Reviews at Bruxelles	2 (Feb2020 – Feb2022)

SensApp Project	
Duration	Start: 1 st January 2019 End: 31 st December 2021
Overall budget	3.287.562,50 € (75% pre-paid)
Partners	6
Work Packages	5
Deliverables	24 (12 public; 12 confidential)
Milestones	4
Project Reviews at Bruxelles	2 (Feb2020 – Feb2022)

In memoriam Prof. Siegfried Bauer

<https://www.jku.at/en/institute-of-experimental-physics/soft-matter-physics/about-us/in-memoriam-siegfried-bauer/>

Acronym	Full name	Responsible
CNR	National Research Council, Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems (ISASI)	Simonetta Grilli
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Heidi Ottevaere
PULEJO	IRCCS Centro Neurolesi “Bonino Pulejo”	Emanuela Mazzon
JKU	Universitat Linz, Division of Soft Matter Physics	Martin Kaltenbrunner
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland	Sanna Uusitalo
GIN	Ginolis OY	Markku Känsäkoski

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

Institute of
Applied Sciences and
Intelligent Systems **Science
App**

DI
C
Ma
PI

Dipartimento
di Ingegneria Chimica,
dei Materiali e della
Produzione Industriale
Università degli Studi
di Napoli Federico II

Project management
“p-jet” system
Immunoassay protocols
Physics of fluids

Automation solutions
Liquid handling

VRIJE
UNIVERSITEIT
BRUSSEL

Micro-engineering
Micro-optics

Photonics technologies
Integration
Packaging

JKU

JOHANNES KEPLER
UNIVERSITY LINZ

Pyroelectric polymers
Pyroelectric fields

Immunoassay
Pre-clinical tests

CENTRO NEUROLESI
BONINO PULEJO
IRCCS MESSINA

WP number	WP title	Lead	Duration (months)	Start date	End date
WP1	Management and dissemination	CNR	36	2019-01-01	2021-12-31
WP2	Fixing the basic elements & protocols	CNR	18	2019-01-01	2020-06-30
WP3	Design and micro-engineering of the super-sensor building blocks	VUB	22	2019-03-01	2020-12-31
WP4	Full integration & packaging of the super-sensor	VTT	20	2020-01-01	2021-08-31
WP5	Preliminary tests in a clinical setting	PULEJO	6	2021-07-01	2021-12-31

WP number	Nr. Deliverables
WP1	10
WP2	3
WP3	5
WP4	3
WP5	3
24 Deliverables in total	

Gantt chart

Reporting period

All the tasks are in line with the plan

24 Deliverables in total

Deliverables, Ethics, DMP, Other Reports

WP No	Del Rel. No	Del No	Title	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Nature	Dissemination Level	Est. Del. Date
WP1	D1.1	D1	Logo and webpage	Realization of	CNR	Websites, pa	Public	28 Feb 2019
WP2	D2.1	D11	User requirements specification	The specific	CNR	Report	Confidential	28 Feb 2019
WP1	D1.2	D2	IP agreement	Realization of	CNR	Report	Confidential	30 Jun 2019
WP1	D1.3	D3	Plan for data management	Plan for man	CNR	ORDP: Oper	Confidential	30 Jun 2019
WP2	D2.2	D12	Functional and design specifications	Document w	CNR	Report	Confidential	30 Jun 2019
WP1	D1.4	D4	First plan for dissemination and exploitation	Report with p	CNR	Report	Confidential	30 Dec 2019
WP1	D1.5	D5	Flyers with project targets and first results	Flyers which	CNR	Websites, pa	Public	30 Dec 2019
WP1	D1.6	D6	Technical/scientific review meeting 1 document	Document de	CNR	Report	Public	31 Jan 2020
WP3	D3.1	D14	Design and fabrication of the micro-engineered	The micro-er	VUB	Demonstrato	Confidential	29 Feb 2020
WP2	D2.3	D13	Protocols for DSS-based immunoassays	Document re	CNR	Report	Confidential	30 Jun 2020
WP3	D3.2	D15	Design and fabrication of the integrated pyr	Fabrication of	VUB	Demonstrato	Confidential	30 Jun 2020
WP3	D3.3	D16	Design and fabrication of the integrated det	Fabrication of	VUB	Demonstrato	Confidential	31 Oct 2020
WP1	D1.7	D7	International Symposium	Organization	CNR	Websites, pa	Public	31 Dec 2020
WP3	D3.4	D17	First prototypes of climate chamber module	Realization of	GIN	Demonstrato	Public	31 Dec 2020
WP3	D3.5	D18	First prototype of the three individual layers	Realization of	VUB	Demonstrato	Public	31 Dec 2020
WP4	D4.1	D19	Integrated system for calibration and testing	Integrated sy	VTT	Demonstrato	Public	28 Feb 2021
WP4	D4.2	D20	Performance report	Report about	VTT	Report	Confidential	30 Jun 2021
WP4	D4.3	D21	Cost analysis report	Report on th	VTT	Report	Confidential	31 Aug 2021
WP1	D1.8	D8	Technical/scientific review meeting 2 document	Report of the	CNR	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP1	D1.9	D9	Final plan for dissemination and exploitation	Report on th	CNR	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP1	D1.10	D10	Plan for knowledge management & protection	Preparation of	CNR	Report	Confidential	31 Dec 2021
WP5	D5.1	D22	Report on sensitivity and specificity for Abe	Report conta	PULEJO	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP5	D5.2	D23	Report on sensitivity and specificity for tau	Report conta	PULEJO	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP5	D5.3	D24	Report on sensitivity and specificity for P-tau	Report docu	PULEJO	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021

 = CNR responsibility

All expected Deliverables have been produced in line with the plan

Leader: CNR

	1st year (2019)												2nd year (2020)												3rd year (2021)											
MONTH	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
WP2	T2.1 > D2.1												T2.2 > D2.2												T2.3 > D2.3											
																																D1.10				

Task 2.1 – Sharing the know-how on p-jet and strategies for integration procedures (CNR, VUB, VTT, JKU, GIN)

- Define specifications determined by the application (CNR)
- List the parameters that influence the p-jet (CNR)
- List requirements and limitations of various layers/building blocks
 - loading support (CNR/VUB)
 - optical layer (VUB/VTT)
 - reaction layer (CNR)
 - pyroelectric layer (JKU, CNR)
 - inter-layers (all)

Task 2.2 – First modelling of the liquid meniscus (CNR)

- Investigating physical characteristics of the liquid meniscus (CNR)
- Numerically computing droplet fluid dynamics to determine shape/material of μ -orifice (CNR)

Task 2.3 – Implementation of the DSS-based immunoassays at sub-microliter scale (CNR, PULEJO)

- Use of current p-jet setup, commercial a posteriori fluorescence detection and commercial slides for implementing the immunoassay protocols (A β 1-42; tau; P-tau) to set the protocols with best performance.
- Tests for both a-specific and specific slides (CNR/PULEJO)

List of Deliverables

- done D2.1 User requirements specification
- done D2.2 Functional and design specifications
- D2.3 Protocols for DSS-based immunoassays

Leader: VUB

Task 3.4 – Development of modules for automated super-sensor system (GIN)

- Development and testing of humidity and T controlled climate chamber (GIN)
- Automation of liquid handling (GIN)

Task 3.5 – Proof and testing of the individual micro-engineered building blocks (CNR, VUB, VTT, JKU)

- Three layers will be tested at CNR setup (loading support, pyroelectric/reaction layer, optical detection layer)
(CNR, VUB, JKU, VTT)
- For each calibration curves and LOD value will be determined using biomolecules pre-labelled with commercial dyes (CNR, VUB, JKU, VTT)
- Validation of the detection using the protocols of WP2 (CNR)

List of Deliverables

- D3.1 Design and fabrication of the micro-engineered loading support - DEMONSTRATOR
- D3.2 Design and fabrication of the integrated pyroelectric source - DEMONSTRATOR
- D3.3 Design and fabrication of the integrated detection layer - DEMONSTRATOR
- D3.4 First prototypes of climate chamber module and liquid handling module and specification for the automated system - DEMONSTRATOR
- D3.5 First prototype of the three individual layers for successive full integration - DEMONSTRATOR

Leader: VTT

	1st year (2019)												2nd year (2020)												3rd year (2021)											
MONTH	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
WP4	T4.1																																			
	T4.2																																			
	T4.3																																			

Task 4.1 – Super-sensor packaging and automation (study and realization) (VTT, GIN, JKU)

- Integration of building blocks, adding climate chamber and control electronics (VTT, GIN)
- Alignment check between the μ -orifice and the pyroelectric source (VTT, GIN, JKU)
- Integration of liquid handling modules, climate chamber and read out module into GINs robotic platform (GIN, VTT)
- Development of intuitive user interface (GIN)

Task 4.2 – Calibration and benchmarking of the fully integrated super-sensor system (GIN, VTT, CNR, PULEJO)

- System level testing (GIN, VTT)
- Benchmarking with ELISA using 5 series of calibration samples (CNR, PULEJO)

Task 4.3 – Mass-producibility of the disposable super-sensor building blocks (VTT, VUB)

- Market profile and the competitive landscape are studied for the SensApp super-sensor, mapping of EU ecosystem (VTT, VUB)
- Potential groups and fabrication methods are identified and analysed, incl EU manufacturing capacity study (VUB, VTT)
- Device cost analysis and benchmarking against any existing or developing product is performed (VTT, VUB)

List of Deliverables

D4.1 Integrated system for calibration and testing - DEMONSTRATOR

D4.2 Performance report

D4.3 Cost analysis report

Leader: PULEJO

		1st year (2019)												2nd year (2020)												3rd year (2021)												
MONTH		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	
WP5	T5.1																																					
	T5.2																																					
	T5.3																																					

Task 5.1 – Test for Aβ1-42 (PULEJO, all participants)

- Perform measurements (30 samples) to get sensitivity and specificity of the super-sensor for Aβ1-42

Task 5.2 – Test for tau (PULEJO, all participants)

- Perform measurements (30 samples) to get sensitivity and specificity of the super-sensor for tau

Task 5.3 – Test for P-tau (PULEJO, all participants)

- Perform measurements (30 samples) to get sensitivity and specificity of the super-sensor for P-tau

List of Deliverables

- D5.1 Report on sensitivity and specificity for Abeta1-42
- D5.2 Report on sensitivity and specificity for tau
- D5.3 Report on sensitivity and specificity for P-tau

Leader: PULEJO

		1st year (2019)												2nd year (2020)												3rd year (2021)												
MONTH		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	
WP5	T5.1																																					
	T5.2																																					
	T5.3																																					

Full diagnosis of AD (ELISA in CSF, PET)

Different aliquots of blood for each individual

- Determination of Aβ1-42
- Determination of tau
- Determination of P-tau
- Comparison with calibration curve in T4.2
- Monitoring of false positives and false negatives

WP1 – Management and dissemination

- Logo and webpage
- IP Agreement
- Plan for data management
- First plan for dissemination and exploitation
- Flyers with project targets and first results
- Promotional movie

WP2 – Fixing the basic elements & protocols

- User requirement specifications
- Functional and design specifications
- Immunoreaction protocol for A β 1-40

WP3 – Design and micro-engineering of the super-sensor building blocks

- Identification of the configuration for the loading support
- First identification of pyroelectric layer
- Macro system for the optical detection layer

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

WP1: Management and dissemination
WP leader: CNR

Simonetta Grilli, CNR-ISASI

Management Unit (MU)

- Coordinator (Simonetta Grilli, s.grilli@isasi.cnr.it)
- Accounting manager (Loredana Salzano, s.salzano@isasi.cnr.it)
- Communications manager (Veronica Vespini, v.vespini@isasi.cnr.it)
- Support Project manager (Sara Coppola, s.coppola@isasi.cnr.it)

RESPONSABILITIES

Administration, executive management, interface between partners and EC

Steering Committee (SC)

- Coordinator
- WP leaders

RESPONSABILITIES

Monitoring of the activities, preparation of meetings, approval of reports and deliverables, decisions on the progress of activities

WP leaders

RESPONSABILITIES

Technical coordination of the activities, coordination of the researchers' interaction

We have all-female Steering Committee:

- Simonetta Grilli (CNR)
- Heidi Ottevaere (VUB)
- Sanna Uusitalo (VTT)
- Emanuela Mazzon (PULEJO)

SensApp Task 1.1 – Scientific coordination and management

We have set up different means for internal communications:

- Electronic email
- Teleconference
- Phone call
- Slack application
- WhatsApp

We have coordinated the production of:

- Deliverables
- Internal technical documents for monitoring the project progress:
 - Technical reports
 - Short notes
 - Emails (those with significant data, decisions, etc.)
 - Agendas of consortium meetings
 - Minutes of consortium meetings
 - Presentations at the consortium meetings

SensApp Task 1.1 – Scientific coordination and management

We set up the sharing of internal documents in the LOGIN area of www.sensapp.eu

The image shows a screenshot of the SensApp website and its internal file sharing interface. The website header includes the SensApp logo, a navigation menu with items like HOME, PROJECT, TEAM, TECHNOLOGY, AGENDA, NEWS, PUBLICATIONS, JOB OPPORTUNITIES, GALLERY, and LOGIN (circled in red), and the European Union logo. Below the header is a login form with fields for 'Username or email' and 'Password', and a 'Share by link' button. A red arrow points from the 'LOGIN' link in the header to the login form. Another red arrow points from the 'Share by link' button to a file sharing interface. The file sharing interface shows a list of files and folders, including '1st YEAR REVIEW MEETING (2020.02.19, Brussels)', 'bibliography', 'ethics', 'Grant Agreement', 'meetings & calls', 'photos', 'WP1 - Management and Dissemination', 'WP2 - Fixing the basic elements & protocols', 'WP3 - Design and micro-engineering of the super-sensor building blocks', 'WP4 - Full integration & packaging of the super-sensor', 'WP5 - Preliminary tests in a clinical setting', and 'Deliverables List.bmp'. The interface also shows a sidebar with 'All files', 'Favorites', 'Shared with you', 'Shared with others', and 'Tags'.

Name	Size	Modified
1st YEAR REVIEW MEETING (2020.02.19, Brussels)	17.7 MB	4 days ago
bibliography	0 KB	a year ago
ethics	0 KB	a year ago
Grant Agreement	16.3 MB	14 days ago
meetings & calls	59.3 MB	12 days ago
photos	76 KB	a year ago
WP1 - Management and Dissemination	38.9 MB	14 days ago
WP2 - Fixing the basic elements & protocols	22.2 MB	14 days ago
WP3 - Design and micro-engineering of the super-sensor building blocks	1.9 MB	7 days ago
WP4 - Full integration & packaging of the super-sensor	0 KB	a year ago
WP5 - Preliminary tests in a clinical setting	0 KB	a year ago
Deliverables List.bmp	4.5 MB	a month ago

	1st YEAR REVIEW MEETING (2020.02.19, Brussels)
	bibliography
	ethics
	Grant Agreement
	meetings & calls
	photos
	WP1 - Management and Dissemination
	WP2 - Fixing the basic elements & protocols
	WP3 - Design and micro-engineering of the super-sensor building blocks
	WP4 - Full integration & packaging of the super-sensor
	WP5 - Preliminary tests in a clinical setting
	Deliverables List.bmp

- We have created a community on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=sensApp>
- We established this community as the main repository for making datasets publicly available

SensApp Task 1.1 – Scientific coordination and management

zenodo

Log in to account

Log in with GitHub

Log in with ORCID

— OR —

Email Address

Password

Log In

https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=sensapp

zenodo Search Upload Communities v.vespini@isasi.cnr.it

Communities created and curated by Zenodo users

sensapp

Showing 0 to 1 out of 1 communities. Sort by

SensApp H2020 FET OPEN Project "Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma" View Curate

This is the collection of materials created within the "SensApp: Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma", H2020 Research and Innovation Action (Grant Agreement 829104). <http://www.sensapp.eu/>

My communities New

SensApp H2020 FET OPEN Project "Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma" Actions

Identifier: sensapp_h2020_project

https://zenodo.org/deposit/new

Additional notes Optional

License required

Access right *

- Open Access
- Embargoed Access
- Restricted Access
- Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

License * Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Required. Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the *Other* licenses available (*Other (Open)*, *Other (Attribution)*, etc.). The supported licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org and sdx.org. If you think that a license is missing from the list, please contact us.

Funding recommended

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants European Commission (EU) Start typing a grant number, name or abbreviation... x

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the *Additional Notes* field.
Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

Consortium Agreement (CA):

- We prepared the document with the contribution of all partners
- We used the model DESC2020
- We agreed here on different issues such as:
 - Internal organization
 - Expected contributions
 - IP arrangements
 - Rules for management of internal disputes
- The document was undersigned by all partners
- The CA is an internal document

IP Agreement (IPA):

- We have produced this document by taking the appropriate contents from the CA
- This document corresponds to the Deliverable D1.2

Scheme model for the Consortium Agreement

Section 1: Definitions

Section 2: Purpose

Section 3: Entry into force, duration and termination

Section 4: Responsibilities of Parties

Section 5: Liability towards each other

Section 6: Governance structure

Governance structure for Medium and Large Projects

Section 7: Financial provisions

Section 8: Results

Section 9: Access Rights

Section 10: Non-disclosure of information

Section 11: Miscellaneous

Section 12: Signatures

[Attachment 1: Background included]

[Attachment 2: Accession document]

[Attachment 3: List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to Section 8.2.2.]

[OPTION: Attachment 4: Identified Affiliated Entities according to Section 9.5]

[Module GOV SP]

[MODULE IPR SC]

Specific Software provisions

Sections in bold correspond to IPA

Contents of the IP Agreement:

- Confidentiality
- Background selection
- Use of IP generated parallel to the project
- Ownership/joint ownership of results
- Legal protection of results
- Exploitation of results and access rights

More details for period M1-M12 in two deliverables:

- D1.2 IP Agreement
- D1.3 Plan for data management

- The coordinator (Simonetta Grilli) is in contact with the Project Officer (Ioannis Fiamegkos)
- She keeps all partners constantly updated by email
- The account manager will validate the financial statements on the platform
- The coordinator has collected the internal reports
- The coordinator has promoted the internal communications (see Task 1.1 for details)

The coordinator:

Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems
(National Research Council of Italy)

Acronym: CNR-ISASI

- CNR is a single legal person
- CNR is made of more than 90 Institutes throughout Italy
- Only ISASI is involved in this project

- The group of Prof. **Pier Luca Maffettone** cooperates with CNR-ISASI on the Task 2.2
- Expertise: Physics of Fluids
- Affiliation: University Federico II, Department of Chemical Engineering, Materials, Industrial Production

Pier Luca Maffettone

Gaetano D'Avino

Marco Trofa

- The coordinator organized the kick-off meeting on M2 in the headquarter of CNR-ISASI [2019.02.13]
- The coordinator has organized in cooperation with the hosting partner the following meetings:
 - 1st Progress Meeting -> VUB (Brussels) [2019.07.01]
 - 2nd Progress Meeting -> JKU (Linz) [2019.12.17]
 - Upcoming 3rd Progress Meeting -> VTT [2020.09.15]
- The coordinator prepared the minutes of the meetings with the support of the partners

	1st year (2019)												2nd year (2020)												3rd year (2021)											
MONTH	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec

Kick-off meeting at CNR-ISASI
(Pozzuoli, Italy)

1st Progress Meeting at VUB
(Brussels, Belgium)

2nd Progress Meeting at JKU
(Linz, Austria)

- The coordinator promoted the interaction between partners through bilateral meetings on specific Tasks
- The wide amount of bilateral discussions was done in phone call for discussing the intermediate results
- We promoted best-practice examples for the attraction of female researchers

No Deliverables
were expected in this Task
for the reporting period M1-M12

The coordinator constructed the logo of the project for dissemination purposes:

SensApp

- We produced the logo very soon (M2)
- We encourage its use in public events and documents related to the project (websites of the local institutions; presentations; etc.)
- The logo is important for fixing the identity of the project
- The logo captures the vision and recalls graphically the main features of the project

We have constructed the website of the project

www.sensapp.eu

- The website has been established quickly after the kick-off meeting and is continuously updated by the coordinator
- It is a central tool to communicate and disseminate information about the project
- It provides a constant source of information for the interested stakeholders

- The coordinator constructed the social accounts of SensApp
- The coordinator collects materials from consortium and publish on social accounts (e.g. photos; presentations; flyers; news; etc.)
- The coordinator encourages the partners to follow and re-launch the messages published by SensApp accounts

For dissemination purposes the coordinator encourages the partners to use:

- The sentence below (according to the Grant Agreement)
- The right emblem for EU

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 829104”.

OK

- We have produced two flyers on M2 and M12
- They are downloadable on www.sensapp.eu

Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers

What is SensApp

Research project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme, FET- Open Action. SensApp seeks to develop a bench-top "super-sensor" able to detect biomarkers of Alzheimer's disease in plasma.

Why

The detection of biomarkers in body fluids is of great importance for the early diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease. The clinical practice uses typically immunoassay methods, for biomarker determination. Unfortunately, these techniques fail dramatically in a wide variety of cases where the concentration of biomarkers falls below the limit of detection.

Aims

The aim of our project is to develop a very sensitive sensor that will allow us to detect biomarkers of Alzheimer's disease through a simple blood test, for very early and non-invasive diagnosis in routine clinical practice.

How

SensApp develops an outstanding innovative technology that will be involved in those clinical studies where the detection of low abundant biomarkers is of vital importance for the welfare of society. In particular,

- An integrated micro-system in polar materials will split the mother drop of the plasma sample in tiny droplets through electric fields and will accumulate them on a microscale site, while an innovative integrated optical system that will detect the fluorescence signal directly on the reaction support.
- The super-sensor will be fully automated and cost-effective.

Who

SensApp is an interdisciplinary collaboration across Europe.

Coordinator: CNR-ISASI
Consortium: 6 EU partners
Timeframe: 3 Years (Jan 2019 - Dec 2021)
Budget: ~ 3,3 ME
E-mail: sensapp_h2020@univie.ac.at
Website: www.sensapp.eu

Follow us:

CONSORTIUM

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under agreement N° 829104.

This document reflects only the author's view. The European Agency and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

First brochure on M2 (with objectives)

Consortium

The coordinator
National Research Council of Italy (CNR)
Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems (ISASI)
Pozzuoli (Naples), ITALY

Simonetta Grilli, PhD
simonetta.grilli@cnr.it

Partners

- Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Belgium)
- IRCCS Centre "Bonino Pulejo" (Italy)
- Johannes Kepler Universität Linz (Austria)
- VTT Technical Research Centre (Finland)
- Ginolis Ltd. (Finland)

General information

Start date
1st January 2019

End date
31st December 2021

Duration
3 years

Total funding
€ 3 287 562,50

Programme
H2020 – FET Open

Funding scheme
RIA

Follow the project on:
www.sensapp.eu

sensapp.H2020@gmail.com

[@SensApp_H2020](https://twitter.com/SensApp_H2020)

[Facebook](#) [Instagram](#) [YouTube](#)

SensApp

Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach

The SensApp project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 829104

Flyer on M12 with first results (external)

The Alzheimer's disease (AD)

AD is a neurodegenerative disorder that causes progressive and irreversible death of brain cells. The World Health Organization Report reports alarming growth estimates of dementia: 35.6 million cases in 2010 that will double in 2030 and triple in 2050 with 7.7 million new cases per year

The diagnosis

Clinicians make a diagnosis by detecting biomarkers (Tau, pTau and β Amyloid) in cerebrospinal fluid and by neuroimaging.

Limitations

- Diagnosis procedures are invasive;
- Clinicians cannot determine the AD biomarkers in blood due to low concentration (50-100 pg/mL).

Our mission

SensApp aims at developing a "super-sensor" with **sensitivity below 1 pg/mL**. The super-sensor will detect the AD biomarkers in human plasma.

search for β -Amyloid

droplet-scale assay

The technology

Pyro-electric fields will force the immunoreaction into sub- μ L volumes. The biomarkers will be detected through an outstanding droplet-scale assay.

THE FUTURE

The super-sensor will allow you to make a faster and non-invasive diagnosis of AD simply through a routine blood test. Highly efficient screening programs among the population will be possible.

First year results

- Logo, webpage and social accounts for immediate visibility
- First specifications of the super-sensor, with a target sensitivity in plasma below 1 pg/mL
- Plan for managing the data produced by the project
- Inclusion in Zenodo repository of all public project data
<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=sensapp>
- Complete set of functional characteristics and design of the super-sensor
- Plan with clear strategies for promoting the project and for exploiting the deliverables
- Presentation of the project in more than 5 international events
- 1 master's thesis
- More than 5 press releases

Flyer on M12 with first results (internal)

- The coordinator constructed the first promotional movie on M12 with the cooperation of all partners
- It explains the aims of the project and its impact to disseminate as best as possible the research activities
- It is visible on SensApp channels: website; YouTube; Twitter; Facebook

- The coordinator encouraged the **interaction** and the communication among all partners for a successful dissemination of the results of the project
- All the partners participate in **dissemination activities** by providing the coordinator with press releases, presentations, pictures, video releases, articles, publications, etc.
- We produced a detailed **plan for dissemination and exploitation** at both consortium and project level on M12 (details in D1.4)

- The scientific know-how was transferred to
 - Master students
 - PhD students
 - Research fellows employed full-time in the project
 - Young researchers employed full-time in the project
- The first results have been presented at different local and international events (details in D1.4)

New hires at CNR-ISASI, full-time on the project

Romina Rega

Simona Itri

Physics and Engineering

Martina Mugnano

Danila del Giudice

Biology and biotechnologies

In conclusion, we produced here **three Deliverables**:

- Deliverable D1.1: Logo and webpage
- Deliverable D1.4: First plan for dissemination and exploitation
- Deliverable D1.5: Flyers with project targets and first results and promotional movie

- This task does not produce any real deliverable
- It represents the routine technical support to the previous tasks:
 - Maintenance of the website
 - Update the contents of the website and social accounts
 - Technical support for the organization of the meetings
 - Any other support for project management

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

WP2: Fixing the basic elements & protocols

WP leader: CNR

Task 2.1 Sharing the know-how on p-jet and strategies for integration procedures

Simonetta Grilli, CNR-ISASI

		1st year (2019)												2nd year (2020)												3rd year (2021)												
MONTH		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	
WP2	T2.1	D2.1																																				D1.10
	T2.2							D2.2																														
	T2.3																			D2.3																		

Task 2.1 Sharing the know-how on p-jet and strategies for integration procedures (All)

Speaker: Simonetta Grilli

Task 2.2 First modelling of liquid meniscus (CNR)

Speaker: Simona Itri

Task 2.3 Implementation of the DSS-based immunoassays (CNR, PULEJO)

Speaker: Danila del Giudice

The coordinator has shared
the following contents with all partners

Visit of all partners at CNR labs (ISASI, Pozzuoli)

Thick meniscus

- Jets with large contact area
- Large spots
- Low “accumulation”

Side view of the jet

Thin meniscus

- Jets with narrow contact area
- Spots with reduced area
- High “accumulation”

Side view of the jet

Thick meniscus

- Low “accumulation”

Side view of the jet

Thin meniscus

- Jets with narrow contact area
- Spots with reduced area
- High “accumulation”

Side view of the jet

Example of FL spots with NON comparable size

Example of FL spots with comparable size

Example of FL spots with NON comparable size

Example of FL spots with comparable size

We need repeatable jet size

Example 1:
Three jets for 1 spot

Example 2:
Six jets for 1 spot

- The total volume is different
- The FL spots are not comparable
- We need repeatable total number of jets
- Thermal source and evaporation are crucial

Different focused interactions:

- CNR – PULEJO for the implementation of the immunoreactions
- CNR – VUB for the loading support
- CNR – JKU for the pyroelectric/reaction layer
- VUB – VTT for the optical detection layer
- GIN – VTT – all partners for the full integration

D2.1 – User requirements specification (I)

	Specification
Sample type	plasma
Operating mode	drop
Sample volume	1-10 uL
Sensitivity	Less than 1 pg/mL
Productivity	40-50 min for each test
Analytical parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Beta-amyloid• Tau• P-Tau
Daily control kit for calibration before use	Set of 3 calibration samples with different concentrations: low, medium, high
User interface	Touch screen or manual barcode reader
Power requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 100 – 240 V c.a.• 50/60 Hz• Single phase with earth connection
Noise	No isolation required
Operating temperature	19 – 24 °C

D2.1 – User requirements specification (II)

	Specification
Reagents	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Primary and fluorescence-labelled secondary antibodies for each target molecule• Blocking solution• Washing buffer
External archive	USB interface
Printer interface	YES
Access to digital signature	YES
Data archive capacity	30 – 60 tests
Washable exterior	YES

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

WP2: Fixing the basic elements & protocols

WP leader: CNR

Task 2.2 First modelling of the liquid meniscus

Simona Itri, CNR

Task goals

Modelling physical characteristics of the liquid meniscus in order to give the first inputs to the micro-engineering of the orifice in terms of profile and size.

DI
C
Ma
PI

Dipartimento
di Ingegneria Chimica,
dei Materiali e della
Produzione Industriale
Università degli Studi
di Napoli Federico II

Simulation details

- Pre-processing: Geometry and numerical mesh definition
- Volume-Of-Fluid (VOF) simulations have been done in *OpenFOAM*

Boundary conditions

- **Outflow** on the outlet boundaries
- **Axial symmetry** on the axis of symmetry
- **Slip** with a prescribed contact angle on the walls.

Simulation's output example

PHISYCAL PARAMETERS (WATER/AIR SYSTEM) (fixed)

Droplet dynamic viscosity [=] Pa*s	0.001
Droplet Density [=] Kg/m ³	1000
Surface tension [=] N/m	0.07
Contact Angle [=]°	60°
Air Density [=] Kg/m ³	1
Air Viscosity [=] m ² /s	1.48*10 ⁻⁵

GEOMETRICAL PARAMETERS (variable)

Orifice Inclination	α
Orifice bottom radius	r
Orifice height	H

Investigated conditions

Parameter	Condition 1		Condition 2		Condition 3	
α	1°, 5°, 10°, 20°, 30°, 40°	<u>variable</u>	40°	<u>fixed</u>	40°	<u>fixed</u>
r	0.5 mm	<u>fixed</u>	1 mm, 0.5 mm	<u>variable</u>	0.5 mm	<u>fixed</u>
H	1 mm	<u>fixed</u>	1 mm	<u>fixed</u>	1mm, 1.5 mm	<u>variable</u>

COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

Condition1: variable orifice inclination angle (α)

$\alpha=1^\circ$ $\alpha=5^\circ$ $\alpha=10^\circ$ $\alpha=20^\circ$ $\alpha=30^\circ$ $\alpha=40^\circ$

PARAMETER	VALUE	
r	0.5 mm	fixed
H	1 mm	fixed
α	1°, 5°, 10°, 20°, 30°, 40°	variable

$\forall \alpha$: No significant variations are obtained for the meniscus thickness, which remains around 100 μm .

Inclination angle was fixed at 40°.

Condition2: variable orifice bottom radius (r)

r=1mm

r=0.5mm

PARAMETER	VALUE	
r	1 mm, 0.5 mm	variable
H	1 mm	fixed
α	40°	fixed

- (a): $r=1\text{ mm}$, meniscus thickness $\sim 1\text{mm}$;
 (b): $r=0.5\text{ mm}$, meniscus thickness $\sim 0.1\text{mm}$.

Orifice bottom radius was fixed at 0.5 mm.

Condition 3: variable orifice height (H)

PARAMETER	VALUE	
r	0.5 mm	fixed
H	1 mm, 1.5 mm	variable
α	40°	fixed

(a): $H = 1 \text{ mm}$, meniscus thickness $\sim 0.1 \text{ mm}$;

(b): $H = 1.5 \text{ mm}$, meniscus thickness $\sim 0.1 \text{ mm}$

In the range of values investigated, the orifice height (H) is irrelevant for the meniscus thickness.

Conclusions

- \exists upper limit value of D_b around 1 mm
- $\forall \alpha \in [1^\circ; 40^\circ]$, no significant effect on meniscus thickness
- $H \in [1, 1.5]$, no significant effect on meniscus thickness.

1st batch manufacturing provided by VUB

Inclination, α [=]°	Thickness, H [=] mm	Bottom Diameter, D_b [=]mm	
40	1	1	1.02
		2	1.00
		3	0.88
		4	0.62

University of Naples Federico II

Dispensing pico droplets by pyroelectrohydrodynamic jetting: simulations and experimental results

Department of Chemical, Materials and Production Engineering

Supervisor:
Prof. Pier Luca Maffettone

Candidate:
Anna Faraone
Matr. P16000026

Advisors:
Prof. Gaetano D'Avino
Dr. Simonetta Grilli

ACADEMIC YEAR 2018-2019

The results of these activities in Task 2.2 have been published in the **master thesis of Anna Faraone** downloadable at the SensApp website www.sensapp.eu.

**THANK YOU FOR
YOUR ATTENTION!**

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

WP2: Fixing the basic elements & protocols

WP leader: CNR

Task 2.3 Implementation of the DSS-based immunoassays

Danila del Giudice CNR-ISASI

Alzheimer's disease

**Around 50 million people have dementia,
10 million new cases every year¹**

Early diagnosis is our goal

What is Alzheimer's disease?

Irreversible, degenerative and progressive brain disorder,
with deterioration of cognitive function

Which are the symptoms?

Difficulties with memory, language, problem-solving, difficulty completing familiar task, confusion with time or place, changes of personality

How is diagnosed today?

- Memory test
- Brain imaging test (MRI CT PET)
- CerebroSpinal Fluid analysis

Hallmarks

Neurofibrillary Tangles (NFTs)

Amyloid β ($A\beta$) plaques

Normal
Tau protein

Abnormal
phosphorylated tau (P-Tau)
protein

Hallmarks

Neurofibrillary Tangles (NFTs)
 Amyloid (A β) plaques: A β 1-42

Normal

Cleavage of Amyloid Precursor Protein (APP)

Abnormal

Cleavage of Amyloid Precursor Protein (APP) leading to excess amyloid accumulation

ELISA test is our competitor

Generic indirect assay

Substrate

Enzyme-conjugated
secondary antibody

Primary antibody

Target protein

Our current approach

Our current approach

Alexa Fluor 647
Secondary Antibody

Primary β Amyloid 1-40
Antibody

Protein target
 β Amyloid1-40

Inno FL Scanner 710
278 x 457 x 369 mm³ (L x W x H)
Resolution: 5 μ m /pixel

Outline

- ❖ **Reaction support**
- ❖ **Solution for the protein**
- ❖ **Stability of the protein**
- ❖ **Pre-treatment of the reaction support**

Reaction supports

Nitrocellulose

ONCYTE

Manual spots

P-jet spots

[200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$]

[100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$]

[50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$]

β Amyloid 1-40 [50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$]	<Diameter> (μm)	<Intensity> (a.u.)	<SNR>
Manual	3505	201	0,400

SUPERAMMINE

Manual spots

P-jet spots

β Amyloid 1-40 [50 µg/ml]	Diameter (µm)	Intensity (a.u.)	SNR
Manual	3020	122	1,258
p-jet spot (1)	825	890	3,04

Achievement:

FL signal for Ab1-40 protocol is detectable on:

- 1) Manual spots on Superamine
- 2) P-jet spots on Superamine

Lacks:

- 1) Low SNR for both kinds of spots
- 2) Diameter of p-jet spots are only 3-fold shorter than manual
- 3) FL signal concentration of p-jet spots is too low

Solution for the protein

Solution	<Diameter> (μm)	<Intensity> (a.u.)	<SNR>	Innoscan image
Glycerol	-	No signal	-	
Tween	-	No signal	-	
Triton	-	No signal	-	
PMRB	2260,92	544,28	1,93	
DMSO	806,05	16,871	0,563	
dH₂O	288	544	19,75	

Stability of the protein

β Amyloid 1-40 [50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$] in dH_2O
 β Amyloid 1-40 [50 ng/ml] in dH_2O
 β Amyloid 1-40 [500 pg/ml] in dH_2O

$\text{A}\beta_{1-40}$ Concentration	Column	Row	Diameter (μm)	Intensity (a.u.)	SNR	<Intensity> (a.u.)
500 pg/ml	1	1	301	982	25.47	
	1	2	192	1041	11.25	934
	1	3	163	796	5.77	
50 ng/ml	2	1	513	460	2.85	
	2	2	472	404	5.04	456
	2	3	775	504	6.54	
50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	3	1	175	245	1.17	
	3	2	153	183	2.01	193
	3	3	192	150	1.68	

THERE IS NO LINEAR CORRESPONDENCE BETWEEN PROTEIN CONCENTRATION AND FLUORESCENT SIGNAL!

Pre-treatment of the reaction support

- Concentration in dH₂O = 50 µg/mL

ACTIVATED	Row	Diameter (µm)	Intensity (a.u.)	SNR
	1	380	1187	6
	2	450	743	30
	3	175	608	6

NO ACTIVATED	Row	Diameter (µm)	Intensity (a.u.)	SNR
	1	100	3092	450
	2	100	4667	526
	3	90	2054	196

Conclusions

Reaction support: Superamine

Solvent for the protein: dH₂O

Storage for the protein solution: 4°C

Pre-treatment of the reaction support: No Activation

Next step

Alexa Fluor 647
Secondary Antibody

Second Antibody

Protein target

Primary Antibody

Thank you for your attention

*More diagnosis means
more awareness.*

*More awareness
means less stigma.*

*Less stigma means
more hope.*

Materials

ONCYTE support item: 705278

SuperAmine Catalog ID: SMM2

B Amyloid 1-40 Fragment : sigma A1075

Blocking solution: Grace Bio-Labs' Super G Protein Array Blocking Buffer

Blocking solution: BlockIt Blocking buffer Arrayit cat. BKT, Lot.N.: 150421

Primary Ab B Amyloid : antirabbit thermofisher 44136

Secondary Ab antirabbit : thermofisher A32733, 647 alexa fluor

Innoscan 710 microarray scanner

Protein Microarray Activation Buffer Catalog ID: PMAB

Protein Microarray Wash Buffer Catalog ID: PMWB

Protein Microarray Rinse Buffer Catalog ID: PMRB

Protein Microarray Reaction Buffer Catalog ID: PMRBP

Mini PAP Pen Invitrogen Lot No.: 75803198A

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

WP3: Design and micro-engineering of the super-sensor building blocks

WP leader: VUB

Heidi Ottevaere, VUB

Overview of WP3 tasks

T3.1	The loading support	VUB
T3.2	The pyroelectric/reaction layer	JKU
T3.3	The integrated optical detection layer	VUB, VTT
T3.4	Development of modules for automated super-sensor system	GIN
T3.5	Proof and testing of the micro-engineered building blocks	CNR, VUB, VTT, JKU

Task 3.1 Development of the loading support

The loading support

Target spot diameter (5μm – 50μm)

Hesaglas PMMA

- Numerical modeling to form the optimal orifice shape (CNR)
- Material selection
 - Manufacturability
 - Wettability (hydrophilic or hydrophobic)

	Full name	Contact angle (water on sample) *
PMMA	Poly(methyl methacrylate)	68-72 °
COC	Cyclic olefin copolymer	88 ± 3°
PC	polycarbonate	82°
PS	Polystyrene	87.4°
PDMS	poly(dimethyl siloxane)	107.2°

* Critical Surface Tension and Contact Angle with Water for Various Polymers, "https://www.accudynetest.com/polytable_03.html?sortby=contact_angle"

Task 3.1 Development of the loading support

1st Manufacturing result

Material: Hesaglas PMMA

Diamond tooling

Target*: Bottom diameter varies from 1mm to 0.1mm

No.	Top Diameter	Bottom Diameter
1	5mm	1.02mm
2	5mm	1mm
3	5mm	0.88mm
4	5mm	0.62mm

- use Hesaglas PMMA as the loading support materials.
- Difficult to cut < 0.5mm bottom orifice directly.

Task 3.1 Development of the loading support

2nd Manufacturing result

(i)

(iii)

(ii)

(iv)

- (i) Use CNC to mill and cut the upper and bottom mold
- (ii) Hot embossing to generate the micro-orifice slabs
- (iii) –(iv) Diamond tooling to cut the slabs with desired heights

No.	Thickness	Bottom Diameter	Plasma
1	2.77mm	0.46mm	Yes
2	2.81mm	0.36mm	Yes
3	2.84mm	0.32mm	Yes
4	2.79mm	0.44mm	No
5	2.83mm	0.35mm	No
6	2.88mm	0.29mm	No

- Current micro-orifice diameter \geq **0.3mm**.
- The surface PV is lower than **1 μ m**.
- Suitable for **mass-production**, loading support can be **disposable**.

Task 3.2 Development of the pyroelectric/reaction layer

Results of 9µm thin PVDF foil (like other thicknesses)

- **Characterize PVDF with different thicknesses**
 - **Laser Induced modulation Method (LIMM)**
- Study external electric field produced by thermally stimulated pyroelectric elements
 - Designed a Laser machined micro-heater for repeatable experiments.
 - Demonstrated on thin film elements made by different materials: LiNbO₃, PVDF, etc.
 - PVDF reveals unfavorable charge trapping effect than LiNbO₃.
- Investigated reaction layers and their influence on electric field.

Task 3.2 Development of the pyroelectric/reaction layer

experimental setup

- **Study external electric field produced by thermally stimulated pyroelectric elements**
 - **Designed a Laser machined micro-heater for repeatable experiments.**
 - Demonstrated on thin film elements made by different materials: LiNbO₃, PVDF, etc.
 - PVDF reveals unfavorable charge trapping effect than LiNbO₃.
- Investigated reaction layers and their influence on electric field.

Task 3.2 Development of the pyroelectric/reaction layer

Thermal pulse ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) of the micro heater and temporal evaluation (V) of corresponding surface potential

130 μm PVDF foil

0.5mm ViNbO3 plate

- Demonstrated on thin film elements made by different materials: LiNbO₃, PVDF, etc.
- PVDF reveals unfavorable charge trapping effect than LiNbO₃.
- Investigated reaction layers and their influence on electric field.

Task 3.2 Development of the pyroelectric/reaction layer

Theoretical FEM calculations

Infinite field strength at the edges of the pyroel. element

Effect of reaction layer

weak field attenuation by **Super Amine** glass slide

- Investigated reaction layers and their influence on electric field.

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

278 x 457 x 369 mm³ (L x W x H)
 Inno FL Scanner 710: CNR
 Resolution: 3-40um /pixel

- Very compact micro-optics:
 11 x 4 x 6mm³ (L x W x H)
- Ideal design -> realistic demonstration using off-the-shelf components

900 x 800 x 380 mm³ (L x W x H)
 Typhoon FL scanner: VTT
 Resolution: 10 μm, 25 μm, 50 μm, 100μm
 or 200μm /pixel

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Macro-built demo setup to characterize functionalities

(b) Setup

Optical path - confocal configuration to ensure **high SNR**

- Light source: 635nm laser or LED, possible angle adjustments
- Sample slide: SuperAmine (or 2D Amino) or ONCYTE
 - XY translation stage: 110mm x 75mm, 250 mm/s velocity
 - Z adjustable stage: 13mm range
- Microscope objective: NA 0.25, 10x, WD 17mm
- Emission filter: CWL 680nm, BW 42nm
- Tube Lens: 180mm EFL, WD 130mm
- Pinholes: 50 μ m, 400 μ m, 800 μ m
- Detector: PMT or μ PMT

Preliminary tests

- to investigate the suppression of background noise by using a pinhole.
- to check X, Y tolerance (alignment precision) and Z tolerance (autofocus or not).
- to determine the limit of detection and test photobleaching effects.

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Development of the macro-built demo setup

Top view

- Automated XY scanning stage with customized LabVIEW-based control software on laptop
- Adjustable laser position and angle to maximize the excitation light intensity
- Adjustable stage Z position to find the best foci

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Determine Limit of Detection (LOD): samples preparation

- AIM of the study was to determine the current limit of detection with slanted angle illumination and confocal imaging
- Commercial inkjet printer was used to produce small sample spots to test demo set-up
- Several sample slides were produced using both ONCYTE slides and 2D-Amino slides

Details of different samples used in study

- Fluorophore or fluorophore labelled antibody
- **FL concentrations in buffer:** 1:100, 1:250, 1:500, 1:1000
- **FL Antibody concentrations in buffer:** 0.08mg/ml, 0.04mg/ml, 8µg/ml, 0.8µg/ml
- Buffer: IPA+ Tween 20 in PBS
- **Different spot spacings:** 4mm, 2mm, 1mm and 0.5mm for FL 1:100

Benchmark: Image of one sample slide scanned by Typhoon FL imager
8 FL blocks with 9 sample spots/block

FL spots by inkjet printing

- 9 spots per block: 3x3 array
- 4 pL volume/spot

Typhoon parameters:

- Laser 635nm
- Filter Cy5 670BP30
- PMT 500V/350v
- Image pixel size 10µm

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Determine Limit of Detection (LOD): experimental results

PA7_3A1_uPMT_gain0.9v_pinhole400um_Res30um

(a) 0.04 mg/ml

PA7_5A1_uPMT_gain0.9v_pinhole400um_Res40um

(b) 8 µg/ml

PA7_7A1_uPMT_gain1v_pinhole400um_Res30um

(c) 0.8 µg/ml

- 0.8 µg/ml is almost the LOD for both the demo-setup and Typhoon imager
- Not yet reaching the target 1pg/ml
- Improve the SNR by two tracks:
 - enhance signal (p-jetting, improve collection efficiency)
 - reduce noise (photon counter)

0.8 µg/ml by Typhoon imager

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Characterize noise: sample slide scattering

When lighting $\theta = 60^\circ$, ONCYTE has about 10^7 counts regarding detector at 0° .

Ideal diffuse reflection
Lambertian

Diffuse reflection with
Mirror-like

When lighting $\theta = 60^\circ$, SA has about 10^6 counts regarding detector at 0° , about 10 times less than ONCYTE.

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Characterize noise: auto fluorescence of optical components

- 16 polymer samples, ONCYTE slide, Super Amine slide and microscope slide
- Low auto-fluorescence values enable lower noise
- Several materials showed low auto-FL levels
 - Hesaglas PMMA
 - Amine coated slide
- ONCYTE has much higher auto FL than Amine coated slide

Sample	Average Intensity [counts]
Background signal Typhoon	113
Microscope slide	188
PMMA Hesaglas 0.5 mm	189
PMMA Hesaglas 0.8 mm	209
SuperAmine	229
PMMA Casted	231
PMMA Hesaglas, 1.5 mm	249
PMMA Hesaglas 1.5 mm	251
PMMA Hesaglas 2 mm	267
Topas COC 5013, 1.5 mm	328
Topas COC 6013, 1.5 mm	477
Topas COC 8007, 3 mm	698
PMMA	816
Topas COC 6117, 1.5 mm	940
PMMA Hesaglas 1.5 mm	1052
Polystyrene, square sample	1074
ONCYTE	1252
Polystyrene, round sample	1377
PMMA Extruded	2917
Polycarbonate	19129

Characterize slide noise with the demo setup

Gains	Blank Amine slide	Blank ONCYTE slide
0.5v, G5	1.29mV	2.65mV
0.6v, G5	1.36mV	13.86mV
0.7v, G5	1.36mV	69.51mV
0.8v, G5	1.37mV	290.75mV
0.9v, G5	1.31mV	949.43mV
1.0v, G5	1.31mV	2330mV

- Conclusion
 - Amine coated slide is better than ONCYTE regarding Auto FL and Background noise.
 - PMMA will be used to manufacture the micro-optics.

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Reduce signals loss from photobleaching

One FL spots was 'turned off' after 10 minutes of laser excitation

- Photobleaching decreases the FL signal significantly due to locally high laser power.
- In 1min, the signal loss is ~ 33%.
- ✓ need camera to locate spots
- ✓ less time of laser excitation over spots
- ✓ more uniform laser

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

New design with a camera to find the tiny 'spot'

Lessons learnt from the demo setup experiments

- Select laser with better beam parameters
- Illumination should be more uniform to make a constant measurement
- Add shutter to avoid unnecessary laser excitation during alignment
- Improve NA of the objective lens to collect more fluorescent signals
- Fewer components with low auto FL materials to increase transmission while keeping low noise
- Monitor camera with 455nm LED illumination to avoid excitation of the FL spots (less photobleaching)
- XY tolerance: 10 μm , Z tolerance: 10 μm (Autofocus is required to ensure better SNR)

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Optical design of Illumination path

Input laser: **gaussian beam**, Diameter = 3mm

Output **flat-top beam**, Diameter = 0.2mm

- Two freeform surfaces to manipulate laser distribution
- Achieve a quasi-uniform Illumination in the center

Task 3.3 Development of the integrated optical detection layer

Optical design of collection path

Surface 8: pinhole

Spot Diagram

2/6/2020
 Units are μm . Airy Radius: 0.981 μm . Legend items refer to Wavelengths

Field	: 1
RMS radius	: 0.031
GEO radius	: 0.116

- Well focused spot indicates that the collected FL signals can pass the pinhole to reach detector
- All the noise from outside the FL spot will be eliminated by the pinhole
- NA increased by 2.8x, signal increased by 7.8x**
- Dimension: 12mm x 12mm x 35mm

Task 3.5 Testing of individual micro-engineered building blocks

From Oct. to Dec. 2019, CNR has tested two different configurations for the loading support to explore the best droplet repeatability.

OPTION 1: *Orifice*

1st manufacturing and 2nd manufacturing

- Different bottom diameters (manufactured by VUB in Task 3.1, seen in slide #4 and slide #5)
- Different wettability

OPTION 2: *Orifice-pin*

Orifice ($D_b=1\text{mm}$) + ArrayIt[®] pin(SMP3)

D_b (bottom diameter)

Task 3.5 Testing of individual micro-engineered building blocks

OPTION 1: *Orifice* 1st manufacturing

Schematic view of the p-jet tests by the bulk set-up

Initial state

During the stimulation

Droplets dispensing

Load of the mother drop in the orifice
Formation of the liquid meniscus

Activation of electric field by the pyroelectric effect
Taylor cone formation

Split the mother drop in tiny droplets and dispensed on μ -site of the reaction slide

Task 3.5 Testing of individual micro-engineered building blocks

Sample: β -Amyloid 1-40 in dH₂O (50 ug/mL)

Loading support: orifice bottom diameter $D_b = 0.62$ mm

OPTION 1: Orifice
1st manufacturing

We performed p-jet tests with different mixing buffers to investigate the effect of surface tension on droplet formation

Loading supports with larger bottom diameter (1mm; 1.02mm; 0.88mm) produced unacceptable drop dispensing

Task 3.5 Testing of individual micro-engineered building blocks

**OPTION 1: Orifice
1st manufacturing**

Single spot	Diameter	Repeatability
20 stacked droplets 20 min	~250µm	Low

Task 3.5 Testing of individual micro-engineered building blocks

OPTION 2: Orifice-pin

ArrayIt[®] microarray pin (SMP3)

Orifice slab ($D_b=1\text{mm}$) and pin combined by a frame

Task 3.5 Testing of individual micro-engineered building blocks

OPTION 2: *Orifice-pin*

Initial state

Droplet dispensing

Single spot	Diameter	Repeatability
20 stacked droplets	~100µm	High
4 min		

- ❖ Volume loaded: 4-6 µL
- ❖ No buffer used: dispensing of aqueous solution works well

Aβ1-40 in dH ₂ O	Spot label	Spot diameter(um)	Intensity(a.u.)	SNR
50 µg/mL	1	100	3092	450
	2	100	4667	526
	3	90	2054	196

Achievements of reporting period 1 (M1-M12)

- Macro setup clearly defines the specifications, which help us understand the limits of each components and improve the miniature prototype design.
- By characterizing the noise sources, we can reduce the noise level of the final prototype by **10x**. Besides, a lower-noise detector can be selected.
- By improving the collecting path using freeform optics, we come up with an optical design that performs **7.8x** better than the macro setup.
- By using P-jet technique, we plan to further enhance the LOD by **10^6 x**.
- With a more uniform laser beam, the system tolerance is lessened.
- With a laser shutter and a monitor camera without exciting the FL sample, the photobleaching can be relieved.

Upcoming deliverables and milestones

	Title	Type	Due
D3.1	Design and fabrication of the micro-engineered loading support	Demonstrator	28/02/2020
D3.2	Design and fabrication of the integrated pyroelectric source	Demonstrator	30/06/2020
D3.3	Design and fabrication of the integrated detection layer	Demonstrator	31/12/2020
D3.4	First prototype of climate chamber module and liquid handling module and specification of the system	Demonstrator	31/12/2020
D3.5	First prototype of the three individual layers for successive full integration	Demonstrator	31/12/2020
M3	Integrated individual building blocks	Field survey and Data quality validated	31/12/2020

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

WP4: Full integration and packaging of the super-sensor WP leader: VTT

Sanna Uusitalo, VTT

AIM of the WP4 Full integration and packaging of the super-sensor

Task 4.1 Packaging and automation: 3 modules for building block integration: VTT, GIN with support from CNR, VUB and JKU

- Climate chamber(GIN)
- Modular robot platform (GIN)
- Development of control software, mechanics and electronics for prototype (VTT, GIN)

Task 4.3 Mass-producibility: Estimation for manufacturing costs (VTT, VUB, GIN)

- A simple cost model
- Prediction of fabrication costs
- Market profile and the competitive landscape

Task 4.2 Calibration and benchmarking: Evaluation of performance

- A series of calibration samples for each biomarker (Aβ1-42, tau, P-tau)
 - Preliminary laboratory testing at VTT
 - Laboratory testing with calibration samples at CNR

WP list	H1/2019	H2/2019	H1/2020	H2/2020	H1/2021	H2/2021
WP1	[Progress bar]					
WP2	[Progress bar]					
WP3	[Progress bar]					
WP4		[Progress bar]				
WP5						[Progress bar]

Prototype concept:

Loading module

Single-use reaction slide:

- 1 assay per slide
- Bar code for Ag and patient info
- 5 patient samples per slide
- 3 Ag reaction slides disease diagnostics

Single-use Loading layer:

- μ -Orifice and pin-insert
- One loading layer per patient sample
- 7 loading layers for one assay
- 21 loading layers for 3 assays

Multi-use pyro-layer in a frame:

- Heater element for pyro-electric effect
- 1-3 mm LiNbO₃ crystal for electric field generation

Liquid handling module

Automation with robot:

- Automated pipetting for buffer dispensing and washing steps
- Incubation station for Room Temp incubations
- Slide transfer to external 4°C incubation

Ginolis Delilah
Automation Platform

Read-out module

Alignment control :

- Camera imaging and LED illumination
- Slanted angle laser illumination with flat top beam

Sensitive detection:

- Confocal configuration for low SNR
- High NA optics
- μ PMT or Photon counter detector

Loading module with P-jet

Operation time 70 minutes/slide, 60-70% humidity, 25 °C temp

Capacity to process
10 patient samples/day

Liquid handling module with robot

Processing time 41h, Dark box, 40-60% humidity, 15-25 °C temp

Capacity to process
10 patient samples/day

Read-out module

Operation time 60 min/slide , dark box, 25 °C

Capacity to process
10 patient samples/day

SensApp project prototype and concept of future analysis device

Project prototype

- Manual & automated operations
- Manual control for p-jet
- External 4°C fridge
- Motorised translation stages
- Manual wash for multi-use pins in the loading layer

Future device

- Automated operations
- Automated control for p-jet
- Internal 4°C incubation chamber
- Fully automated translation stages
- Single use loading layer with pin

RnD device for testing developed during SensApp-project

Commercially available:
Additional 5-10 years product development needed

Next steps in WP4

Loading module

Optomech design to integrate p-jet system for the prototype

- Compact p-jet implementation
- Compact side-view camera design
- Tolerance analysis for mechanics
- Climate control

Read-out module

Integration of detection layer:

- μ PMT or photon counter detector
- Design for camera imaging system for spot alignment
- Design for sample slide alignment with $\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$ accuracy

Liquid handling module

Automated solutions for assay process

- Automated washing protocol
- Automated sample incubation
- Robotic system design for slide control

Upcoming deliverables and milestones

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Responsible partner	Result	State	Due date
D4.1	Integrated system for calibration and testing	VTT	Demonstr.	Public	28 Feb 2021
D4.2	Performance report	VTT	Report	Confidential	30 Jun 2021
D4.3	Cost analysis report	VTT	Report	Confidential	31 Aug 2021

Milestone number	Milestone name	Responsible partner	Related WPs	Due date	Means of verification
4	M4. Full integration and automation	VTT	WP3, WP4	31 Aug 2021	Data quality validated

SensApp – First Year Review Meeting

Period: 2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31

Brussels, 19th February 2020

WP5: Preliminary tests in a clinical setting
WP leader: PULEJO

**Emanuela Mazzon, IRCCS Centro Neurolesi
Bonino Pulejo**

Alzheimer's disease

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common form of dementia characterized by memory loss, cognitive and behavioural decline.

The Alzheimer's disease is characterized by:

- Accumulation of insoluble forms of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) in plaques in extracellular spaces. $A\beta$ derives by the proteolytic cleavage of amyloid precursor protein (APP), and in particular $A\beta_{42}$ is more prone to aggregation compared to the other $A\beta$ peptides
- Aggregation of the hyperphosphorylated microtubule protein tau in neurofibrillary tangles in neurons

- A β is generated by neurons, microglia and astrocytes in the brain, and by platelets, skin fibroblasts, osteoblasts, and skeletal muscle cells in the periphery
- The central nervous system (CNS) and peripheral pools of A β can interact A β peptides in the CNS are cleared via phagocytosis or proteolytic degradation, whereas others are released into the blood via the blood–brain barrier, interstitial fluid or cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)
- Some A β peptides in blood are phagocytosed by monocytes or neutrophils, some are degraded by A β -degrading enzymes, and some are transported to peripheral organs or tissues.

Neuroimaging

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and Positron Emission Tomography (PET).

Lumbar puncture

Evaluation of $A\beta_{42}$, tau and p-tau in CSF. Ranges:

- $A\beta_{42}$: > 500 ng/L
- Total tau: 0 - 500 ng/L
- P-tau: 0 - 61 ng/L
- Ratio tau/ $A\beta_{42}$ < 0,58
- Ratio p-tau/ $A\beta_{42}$ < 0,12

AT(N) classification

This classification system for AD is based on the presence or the absence of accepted biomarkers that reflect the main pathological hallmarks of AD:

- (A) deposition of $A\beta$
- (T) pathological Tau
- (N) neurodegeneration

The aim is to create a scheme for defining and staging the disease.

	AT (N) biomarker grouping
A	A: Aggregated $A\beta$ or associated pathologic state CSF $A\beta_{42}$ or $A\beta_{42}/A\beta_{40}$ ratio Amyloid PET
T	T: Aggregated tau (neurofibrillary tangles) or associated pathologic state CSF phosphorylated tau Tau PET
N	N: Neurodegeneration or neuronal injury Anatomic MRI fluoro-deoxyglucose (FDG) PET CSF total tau

Aims of SensApp

The aim of SensApp project is to develop a super-sensor with high sensitivity (below 1 pg/mL) in order to detect the AD biomarkers ($A\beta_{42}$, tau, p-tau) in plasma. The traditional ELISA kits cannot determine these biomarkers in plasma due to their abundance well below the standard sensitivity that is of 50-100 pg/mL.

ADVANTAGES

Since lumbar puncture for CSF collection is an invasive procedure, the development of the super-sensor would be desirable to simplify diagnosis and it will overcome the limits of detection usually encountered by standard ELISA protocols.

WP5 specific aims

The aim of WP5 is the collection of blood of AD patients in order to preliminarily test the super-sensor.

The results of the detection of $A\beta_{42}$, tau, p-tau in plasma of AD patients will be compared to those obtained with ELISA from CSF of the same patients, in order to test the sensitivity, specificity and reliability of the super-sensor.

Overview of WP5 tasks

Task 5.1 – Test for Ab1-42 (PULEJO, all participants)

Task 5.2 – Test for tau (PULEJO, all participants)

Task 5.3 – Test for P-tau (PULEJO, all participants)

Overview of WP5 deliverables

D5.1 Report on sensitivity and specificity for Ab1-42

D5.2 Report on sensitivity and specificity for tau

D5.3 Report on sensitivity and specificity for P-tau

